

*A publication of the Department of Library and Information Science,
University of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria*

Artificial Intelligence and Management of Open and Distance Learning Education in Nigeria: Opportunities and Challenges

Abdulkadir Mohammed Saidu

University of Maiduguri, Department of Education

msabdul@unimaid.edu.ng, +2348032828413

Ado Abubakar Adamu

University of Maiduguri, Centre for Distance Learning

adamubnabubakar@gmail.com

Aisha Makinta Wuda

University of Maiduguri, Department of Education

Abstract

Keywords:

Artificial Intelligence, Open and Distance Learning, Management, Opportunities and Challenges

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a disruptive technology that has the potential to alter many elements of Open and Distance Learning Education and Management. This study investigates the opportunities and challenges posed by AI in the context of Open Distance Learning (ODL) in Nigeria.

Methodology

This study delves into the opportunities and challenges of AI in ODL, examining personalized learning experiences, automated assessment and feedback mechanisms, improved accessibility for learners with disabilities, enhanced communication skills, accountability and transparency in educational management, and AI-driven recommendations and adaptive learning systems.

Findings/Results

AI in ODL provides opportunities for personalized learning experiences tailored to individual learners' needs and preferences, automated assessment and feedback mechanisms, and improved accessibility for learners with disabilities. It further improves communication skills, accountability, and transparency in educational management, as well as content and instruction quality through AI-driven recommendations and adaptive learning systems.

Conclusion

AI presents several obstacles for ODL. These challenges include ensuring data privacy, security, and fairness in algorithmic decision-making; bridging the digital divide to ensure equitable access to AI-powered ODL platforms; maintaining the quality and accuracy of AI-generated content and assessments; and addressing ethical concerns about privacy, bias, and algorithmic accountability.

Recommendations

This study emphasizes the significance of ethical and responsible AI implementation in ODL. It makes recommendations to stakeholders in the ODL community on how to maximize the promise of AI while limiting its risks, eventually promoting the aims of accessible, inclusive, and successful distance education.

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) describes how technology, especially computer systems, mimic human intelligence processes. The technologies that support AI are categorized into multiple domains, including big data, machine learning, speech, natural language processing, and computer vision (Chiu, 2021; Chiu et al., 2022; Xia et al., 2022). The rapid expansion of this field is drastically changing how people live, work, learn, engage, manage and communicate (Chiu, 2021; Chiu et al., 2022; Xia et al., 2022; Pedro et al., 2019). Open and Distance Learning (ODL) education gives students who are unable to attend standard classroom sessions in-person flexible learning alternatives. Regardless of a person's location or schedule, it integrates the concepts of openness, flexibility and distance education to support their learning experiences and management.

In Nigeria, Artificial intelligence has brought so many opportunities in areas of Education such as students' activities, lecture note, report and memo writing as well as project writing (Abayomi, 2021; Sanusi et al., 2022), security (Falode et al., 2021), Energy (Mobayo et al., 2021), Health (Muhammad et al., 2021; Anazodo et al., 2022). However, several research pointed out some of the issues that prevent AI from being widely used in Nigeria, including lack of awareness, lack of system or field knowledge, lack of computing resources, and lack of trust in AI as a new tool in education and its management. (Mobayo et al., 2021; Imhanyehor et al., 2021; Okwu et al., 2021).

In this study, AI in Open and Distance Learning (AIODL) refers to the application of AI technologies, such as chatbots, robots, intelligent tutoring systems, and automated evaluation of all forms of digital artifacts that support and enhance virtual learning and management. AIODL fosters teachers' understanding of students' learning processes,

offers students more personalized and adaptive learning, and provides instantaneous feedback and machine-supported queries anywhere, anytime. These features have the potential to significantly improve learning, teaching, assessment, record keeping, communication and administration artificial intelligence in open and distance learning.

1. Artificial Intelligence Opportunities in ODL (AIODL)

AIODL has become a significant emerging research area for laying out the future of teaching and learning as well as management of the sector (Holmes et al., 2021) with the ongoing development of AI technologies and the application of pertinent policies. Its effects are felt in the domains of learning, teaching, assessment, and administration and management of education (Gonzalez-Calatayud et al., 2021; Luckin, 2017). Artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to transform Open Distance Learning (ODL) by providing personalized learning experiences, improving instructional design, ensure accountability and transparency, increasing student support services and records keeping, and enabling efficient administration.

Holmes et al. (2021) note that the effects of artificial intelligence on education and its management are still unknown, and further study is required to determine whether and how these new technologies improve education. Researcher like John, (2022), Khan (2022) and Jark (2021) revealed that AIODL fosters teachers' understanding of students' learning processes, offers students more personalized and adaptive learning, and provides instantaneous feedback and machine-supported queries anywhere, anytime. These features have the potential to significantly improve learning, teaching, assessment, and educational administration. However, It's difficult to introduce or integrate the technologies into education when people are unfamiliar with it

(Hussin, 2018). AI (Artificial Intelligence) has indeed brought both opportunities and challenges to Open and Distance Learning (ODL). Here are some of the challenges that AI presents in the context of ODL:

I. Personalised Learning:

AI enhances ODL student engagement and learning results by adapting instructional materials to individual requirements and learning styles. Hiranker and Kittisunthonphisarn (2020) developed an AI-integrated management system that uses augmented, virtual, and mixed reality technologies to monitor student learning progress and assign adaptive activities; Kong et al. (2021) created a virtual patient for medical student training; Munawar et al. (2018) created and developed an intelligent virtual laboratory to meet students' needs by assigning laboratory tasks at the appropriate level; and Yang and Shulruf (2019) used an AI-enhanced skin to provide real-time feedback and adaptive tasks to medical students.

II. Intelligent Tutoring Systems

AI-based ITS give students with interactive and individualized teaching, as well as real-time feedback, coaching, and remediation depending on their responses and progress. These technologies replicate one-on-one tutoring sessions, improving the efficacy of instruction in ODL settings. Intelligent tutoring systems seek to recommend teaching content and tasks that are suited for specific teaching needs (Aldeman et al., 2021; Bellod et al., 2021; McCarthy et al., 2016; Weragama & Reye, 2014). For example, Luo (2018) and Standen et al. (2020) used AI systems and multimodal sensor data to assess students' affective states and assist teachers in determining the best presentation of information, teaching approaches, and communication tactics. Lampos et al. (2021) employed an artificial intelligence classifier to identify effective

communication tactics for teachers teaching autistic students based on student responses and traits. Crowe et al. (2017) found that teachers altered their teaching tactics depending on quick feedback from an academic writing software package on individual and whole-class processing of learning materials.

III. Natural Language Processing (NLP)

NLP technologies enable ODL systems to understand and reply to students' natural language queries, thereby enabling conversational engagements and giving immediate guidance and feedback. NLP-powered chatbots and virtual assistants can help students navigate courses, troubleshoot issues, and access resources.

IV. Learning Analytics

AI-powered learning analytics solutions analyze massive volumes of student data to uncover patterns, trends, and insights into learning behavior, performance, and consequences. Educators can utilize these insights to improve teaching tactics, anticipate students who are likely to fail, and intervene proactively to help struggling learners in ODL contexts.

AI technologies seem to have helped anticipate student achievement, especially in online education (Akmese et al., 2021; Costa-Mendes et al., 2021; Yu, 2021). They have demonstrated the ability to predict students' performance in online courses by measuring the frequency and quality of their engagement in learning activities such as discussion boards. This functionality is critical for distance education and MOOCs due to the lack of lecturers.

V. Content Creation and Curation

AI algorithms can create and curate educational content, including quizzes, assessments,

interactive simulations, and multimedia resources. These AI-generated products can enrich existing course materials, increase learner engagement, and respond to changing learning demands in ODL settings.

VI. Automated Assessment and Grading:

Artificial intelligence-based assessment technologies automate the grading of assignments, quizzes, and examinations, saving instructors time and providing students with rapid feedback. Machine learning algorithms can accurately assess complicated tasks such as essay writing and problem solving, ensuring consistent and impartial evaluation in ODL.

Our investigation revealed that using AI to enhance and automate evaluation resulted in more effective grading (Aebi & Karal, 2017; Alghamdi et al., 2020; Fu et al., 2020; Kumar & Boulanger, 2020; Ma & Slater, 2015).

AI-enhanced grading systems for language writing, speaking, and mathematics outperformed teachers in terms of test and examination accuracy, speed, and security. In addition, the systems could return immediate marks for formative input in online learning.

VII. Predictive Analytics for Student Success:

AI-powered predictive analytics algorithms examine student data to estimate academic achievement, identify risk factors for dropout or disengagement, and suggest interventions to help students succeed in ODL programs. Early identification of at-risk students allows educators to provide focused support and resources, improving retention rates.

AI technology have supplied educational administrators and management teams with evidence to back up their decisions. AI agents with access to large data can anticipate the likelihood of students dropping their courses,

uncover factors influencing student academic achievement, and support students in course selection (Cukurova et al., 2019; Tsai et al., 2020; Villegas-Ch et al., 2021).

As a result, AI can supply data for administrative decisions and academic advising.

VIII. Administrative Efficiency

AI technology help ODL institutions streamline administrative processes like course scheduling, enrollment management, student support services, and resource allocation. Automated workflows and intelligent technologies maximize resource utilization, eliminate administrative overhead, and boost operational effectiveness.

Our findings show that AI has considerably improved the performance of management systems (Kadhim & Hassan, 2020; Khan & Alotaibi, 2020; Li, 2021; Ruiperez-Valiente et al., 2019; Tang & Hai, 2021; Villegas-Ch et al., 2021). These platforms were made more secure by adding a facial authentication function for exams and portal management (Khan & Alotaibi, 2020; Li, 2020; Liu & Wu, 2019), and administrators were made more effective by assigning AI-enabled routines to tasks such as course scheduling and personnel data management (Li, 2020).

2. Artificial Intelligence Challenges in ODL

i. Personalization and Adaptation: Assessment and Evaluation:

AI can automate the assessment process in ODL by grading assignments, offering comments, and even adjusting assessment difficulty levels based on individual learners. However, assuring the accuracy and impartiality of automated assessment systems is still a difficulty. Furthermore, combating cheating and ensuring academic integrity in online exams is critical.

ii. Access and Inclusivity:

While AI-powered technologies can improve accessibility for learners with disabilities by offering alternative material consumption forms and interactive learning experiences, they also have the potential to exacerbate the digital divide. It is critical that AI-driven ODL platforms are available to all learners, regardless of technological background or resources.

iii. Quality of Content and Instruction:

AI can help ODL platforms by suggesting appropriate learning materials, developing tailored study schedules, and encouraging peer-to-peer learning. However, verifying the quality and accuracy of AI-generated or recommended content is important to ODL programs' legitimacy.

iv. Ethical and Social Implications:

AI poses ethical concerns including privacy, bias, and algorithmic accountability. These problems are especially pertinent in ODL, as AI systems collect and evaluate student data to personalize learning experiences or make academic advancement decisions. Addressing these ethical concerns necessitates transparent regulations, appropriate data governance procedures, and continuous monitoring and evaluation of AI systems.

In this section, some of the major challenges to AI in ODL has been identified:

v. Lack of Relevant Learning Resources for Personalized/Adaptive Learning:

Teachers have complained that the teaching techniques and learning resources provided by personalized/adaptive learning systems are too similar. AI agents recommend learning objects, which are reusable standardized digital instructional resources that can be easily reused and altered to meet a learning purpose in a range of scenarios (Cao et al., 2021). More research is needed to determine how learning objects should be employed in personalized and

adaptive learning, as well as how to improve learning object design for this purpose.

vi. Selecting Appropriate Data for AI Predictive Models:

The well-structured student data employed in present traditional predictive models (linear regressions) may not be suitable for developing AI technologies. An effective AI predictive model necessitates a more thorough set of structured and unstructured student data, raising significant privacy concerns. With AIODL frequently targeting young learners, balancing the effectiveness of AI technology with ethical constraints is critical. More study is needed to determine what types of data should be included in AI models, with careful consideration of ethical concerns (Sharma et al., 2019).

vii. Lack of Connection Between the AI Technologies and their Use in Teaching:

Emerging AI technologies aim to give instructional aid (e.g., through chatbots and robots) as well as rich information to teachers to help them make pedagogical decisions (e.g., learning analytics; Kim et al., 2022). However, this review suggests that teachers may lack a sufficient understanding of the technology to use them successfully. Teachers are sometimes unable to evaluate the information offered by learning analytics, have a limited understanding of the educational benefits of AI technology, and are unsure about the pedagogical consequences of employing AI to teach pupils. For example, should chatbots be utilized to facilitate student conversation before or after a teaching session? Future study should look into the roles of teachers in AI-supported pedagogies.

viii. Lack of Interdisciplinary AI Technologies for Learning:

Because learning is complex, AI systems designed for one discipline may not be helpful

for all student learning. Although AI has several subfields, including natural language processing, computer vision, and neural networks (Chiu, 2021; Chiu et al., 2022; Xia et al., 2022), the AI approaches employed in education are typically straightforward and serve a single objective. The development of AI technology in education is lagging (Bates et al., 2020; Nicolae & Nicolae, 2018). Teachers frequently use off-the-shelf technologies for learning and teaching, which may not be the best fit for their needs. As a result, academics should focus on developing transdisciplinary tools that make advantage of more powerful AI technologies.

ix. **Insufficient Knowledge of AI Technologies Among Teachers:**

Most teachers do not understand how AI technologies work (for example, the principles or algorithms for recommending materials), therefore they have been teaching through a black box. As a result, they are unable to respond to student concerns about AIODL (for example, why the AI platforms selected specific learning resources) and cannot effectively employ the technologies for learning, teaching, and assessment. The need for teachers to have knowledge of AI and its application to pedagogy should therefore be considered in future research.

x. **Negative Attitudes toward AI among Students and Teachers:**

Some students and teachers have described feeling frightened and unsure when studying with AI. Students may grow concerned about their future, as AI technology may render their selected vocations superfluous. Meanwhile, teachers' lack of awareness of the systems can contribute to low self-efficacy (Wang et al. 2020). These uncertainties can lead to negative attitudes about AIODL, influencing behavioral intents to utilize AI to help learning and teaching (Attwood et al., 2020; Qin et al., 2020). More research is needed on AIODL for

students outside of the engineering setting, such as K-12 and art students, as well as teacher professional development on AI subjects (Chiu, 2021; Chiu et al., 2022; Xia et al., 2022; Chai et al., 2022).

Conclusion

Artificial intelligence has changed many sectors and cultures. AI has positively impacted people's lives and wellbeing. However, AI introduces new issues that must be addressed. Given the effect of AI judgments on human lives, users should receive explanations to increase confidence in decisions.

References

- Abayomi, O. K., Adenekan, F. N., Abayomi, A. O., Ajayi, T. A. & Aderonke, A. O. (2021). Awareness and perception of artificial intelligence in the management of university libraries in Nigeria. *Journal of Interlibrary Loan, Document Delivery & Electronic Reserve*, 29(1-2): 13-28. Ad
- Aebi, A.a., & Karal, H. (2017). An application of fuzzy analytic hierarchy process (FAHP) for evaluating students' project. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 12(3), 120–132.
<https://doi.org/10.5897/ERR2016.3065>
- Aldeman, N. L. S., Aita, K., Machado, V. P., da Mata Sousa, L. C. D., Coelho, A. G. B., da Silva, A. S., Mendes, A. P. D., Neres, F. J. D., & do Monte, S. J. H. (2021). Smartpath (k): A platform for teaching glomerulopathies using machine learning. *BMC Medical Education*, 21(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-021-02680-1> <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-021-02870-x>
- Alghamdi, A. A., Alanezi, M. A., & Khan, Z. F. (2020). Design and implementation of a computer aided intelligent examination system. *International Journal of Emerging*

- Technologies in Learning*, 15(1), 30–44.
<https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v15i01.11102>
- Akmese, O. F., Kor, H., & Erbay, H. (2021). Use of machine learning techniques for the forecast of student achievement in higher education. *Information Technologies and Learning Tools*, 82(2), 297–311.
<https://doi.org/10.33407/itlt.v82i2.4178>
- Anazodo, U. C., Adewole, M. & Dako, F. (2022). AI for Population and Global Health in Radiology. *Radiology: Artificial Intelligence*, 4(4): e220107.
- Attwood, A. I., Bruster, B. G., & Bruster, B. G. (2020). An exploratory study of preservice teacher perception of virtual reality and artificial intelligence for classroom management instruction. *SRA Journal*, 29(2). <https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=EJ1268557&site=ehost-live&scope=site>.
- Bates, T., Cobo, C., Marino, O., & Wheeler, S. (2020). Can artificial intelligence transform higher education? *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 17(1), 42.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-020-00218-x>
- Bellod, H. C., RamA³n, V. B., FernA[~]ndez, E. C., & LujA[~]jn, J. F. G. (2021). Analysis of stress and academic-sports commitment through self-organizing artificial neural networks. *Challenges*, 42, 136–144.
<https://doi.org/10.47197/RETOS.V42I0.86983>
- Cao, J. J., Yang, T., Lai, I. K. W., & Wu, J. (2021). Student acceptance of intelligent tutoring systems during COVID-19: The effect of political influence. *International Journal of Electrical Engineering Education*.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/00207209211003270>
- Costa-Mendes, R., Oliveira, T., Castelli, M., & Cruz-Jesus, F. (2021). A machine learning approximation of the 2015 Portuguese high school student grades: A hybrid approach. *Education and Information Technologies*, 26(2), 1527–1547. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-020-10316-y>
- Chiu, T. K. F. (2021). A holistic approach to Artificial Intelligence (AI) curriculum for K- 12 schools. *TechTrends*, 65, 796–807.
- Chiu, T. K. F., Meng, H., Chai, C. S., King, I., Wong, S., & Yeung, Y. (2022). Creation and evaluation of a pre-tertiary Artificial Intelligence (AI) curriculum. *IEEE Transactions on Education*, 65(1), 30–39.
- Crowe, D., LaPierre, M., & Kebritchi, M. (2017). Knowledge based artificial augmentation intelligence technology: Next step in academic instructional tools for distance learning. *TechTrends: Linking Research and Practice to Improve Learning*, 61 (5), 494–506.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11528-017-0210-4>.
- Cukurova, M., Kent, C., & Luckin, R. (2019). Artificial intelligence and multimodal data in the service of human decision-making: A case study in debate tutoring. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 50(6), 3032–3046.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12829>
- Falode, A. J., Faseke, B. O., & Ikeanyichukwu, C. (2021). Artificial Intelligence: The Missing Critical Component in Nigeria's Security Architecture. *LASU Journal of History and International Studies (LAJOHIS)*, 3(1):18-37.
- Fu, S., Gu, H., & Yang, B. (2020). The affordances of AI-enabled automatic scoring applications on learners' continuous learning intention: An empirical study in China. *British Journal of Educational*

- Technology*, 51(5), 1674–1692.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12995>
- Gonzalez-Calatayud, V., Prendes-Espinosa, P., & Roig-Vila, R. (2021). Artificial intelligence for student assessment: A systematic review. *Applied Sciences*, 11(12), 5467.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/app11125467>
- Behaviour*, 1(3).
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-016-0028-0028>.
- Holmes, W., Hui, Z., Miao, F., & Ronghuai, H. (2021). *AI and education: A guidance for policymakers*. UNESCO Publishing.
- Hussin, A. A. (2018). Education 4.0 made simple: Ideas for teaching. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*, 6(3), 92–98.
<https://doi.org/10.7575/aiac.ijels.v.6n.3p.92>
- Imhanyehor, G. O. (2021). Digital Literacy and Primary Educational System in Nigeria. *Journal of Public Administration, Finance and Law*, 10(20):206-221
- Khan, Z. F., & Alotaibi, S. R. (2020). Design and Implementation of a computerized user authentication system for e-learning. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 15(9), 4–18.
<https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v15i09.12387>
- Kong, J. S. M., Teo, B. S., Lee, Y. J., Pabba, A. B., Lee, E. J. D., & Sng, J. C. G. (2021). Virtual integrated patient: An AI supplementary tool for second-year medical students. *Asia Pacific Scholar*, 6(3), 87–90.
<https://doi.org/10.29060/TAPS.2021-6-3/SC2394>
- Kumar, V., & Boulanger, D. (2020). Explainable automated essay scoring: Deep learning really has pedagogical value. *Frontiers in Education*, 5.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2020.572367>
- Lamos, V., Mintz, J., & Qu, X. (2021). An artificial intelligence approach for selecting effective teacher communication strategies in autism education. *NPJ Science of Learning*, 6(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41539-021-00102-x>
- Li, M., & Su, Y. (2020). Evaluation of online teaching quality of basic education based on artificial intelligence. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 15(16), 147–161.
<https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v15i16.15937>
- Liu, J., & Wu, X. (2019). Prototype of educational affective arousal evaluation system based on facial and speech emotion recognition. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 9(9), 645–651. <https://doi.org/10.18178/ijiet.2019.9.9.1282>
- Li, Q. (2021). The use of artificial intelligence combined with cloud computing in the design of education information management platform. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 16(5), 32–44.
<https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v16i05.20309>
- Luckin, R. (2017). Towards artificial intelligence-based assessment systems. *Nature Human*
- Ma, H., & Slater, T. (2015). Using the developmental path of cause to bridge the gap between AWE scores and writing teachers' evaluations. *Writing & Pedagogy*, 7(2–3), 395–422.
<https://doi.org/10.1558/wap.v7i2-3.26376>
- McCarthy, T., Rosenblum, L. P., Johnson, B. G., Dittel, J., & Kearns, D. M. (2016). An

- artificial intelligence tutor: A supplementary tool for teaching and practicing braille. *Journal of Visual Impairment & Blindness*, 110(5), 309–322.
- Muhammad, L. J., & Algehyne, E. A. (2021). Fuzzy based expert system for diagnosis of coronary artery disease in Nigeria. *Health and technology*, 11(2): 319-329.
- Nicolae, M., & Nicolae, E. E. (2018). Leadership in higher education – coping with AI and the turbulence of our times. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Business Excellence*, 12(1), 683–694. <https://doi.org/10.2478/picbe-2018-0061>
- Pedro, F., Subosa, M., Rivas, A., & Valverde, P. (2019). *Artificial intelligence in education: Challenges and opportunities for sustainable development*. Paris: UNESCO.
- Qin, F., Li, K., & Yan, J. (2020). Understanding user trust in artificial intelligence: Evidence from China. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 51(5), 1693–1710. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12994>
- Sanusi, I. T., Olaleye, S. A., Agbo, F. J. & Chiu, T. K. (2022). The role of learners' competencies in artificial intelligence education. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 3:100098. doi: 10.1016/j.caeai.2022.100098.
- Sharma, K., Papamitsiou, Z., & Giannakos, M. (2019). Building pipelines for educational data using ai and multimodal analytics: A "grey-box" approach. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 50(6), 3004–3031. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12854>
- Tsai, S. C., Chen, C. H., Shiao, Y. T., Ciou, J. S., & Wu, T. N. (2020). Precision education with statistical learning and deep learning: A case study in Taiwan. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 17(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-020-00186-2>
- Xia, Q., Chiu, T. K. F, Lee, M., Temitayo I., Dai, Y., & Chai, C.S. (2022). A Self-determination theory design approach for inclusive and diverse Artificial Intelligence (AI) K-12 education, *Computers & Education*, 189, 104582 . doi:10.1016/j.compedu.2022.104582.
- Villegas-Ch, W., Sanchez-Viteri, S., & Rom' an-Ca' nizares, M. (2021). Academic activities recommendation system for sustainable education in the age of COVID-19. *Informatics*, 8(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/informatics8020029>. Article 29.
- Wang, S., Yu, H., Hu, X., & Li, J. (2020). Participant or spectator? Comprehending the willingness of faculty to use intelligent tutoring systems in the artificial intelligence era. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 51(5), 1657–1673. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12998>
- Yang, Y. Y., & Shulruf, B. (2019). Expert-led and artificial intelligence (AI) system-assisted tutoring course increase confidence of Chinese medical interns on suturing and ligature skills: Prospective pilot study. *Journal of Educational Evaluation for Health Professions*, 16. <https://doi.org/10.3352/jeehp.2019.16.7>
- Yu, J. (2021). Academic performance prediction method of online education using random forest algorithm and artificial intelligence methods. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 16(5), 45–57. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v16i05.20297>